

5:6-BENZOQUINALDINIC ACID AS AN ANALYTICAL REAGENT. PART III. ESTIMATION OF ZINC, COBALT, NICKEL AND MANGANESE

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The reagent 5:6-benzoquinaldinic acid has been used for the estimation of zinc, cobalt, nickel and manganese. The points of incipient precipitation for these elements are at about p_H 2.08, 2.14, 2.15 and 1.75 respectively and the respective p_H regions for their complete precipitation are at and over 2.85, 3.24, 3.00 and 2.90. The salt may be dried at 110°-115° and weighed as the hydrated salts, e.g., zinc, with one mole of water, cobalt with two, and both nickel and manganese with two and a half moles of water. The cobalt salt may also be dried at 150°-155° and weighed as the anhydrous salt.

5:6-Benzoquinaldinic acid was used as a reagent for the estimation of copper and its separation from magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, phosphate, arsenite, arsenate, citrate, tartrate etc. (Majumdar and Mallick, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 255) and also for the estimation of cadmium and its separation from copper (Majumdar and De, *ibid.*, 1952, 29, 499). Both copper and cadmium were estimated at p_H over 0.82 and 3.12 respectively and almost all the elements were precipitated by the reagent under different p_H conditions. The present communication comprises the methods for the estimation of zinc, cobalt, nickel and manganese, the study of the p_H ranges over which they are accurately estimated, and the effect of temperature on their salts.

Zinc, cobalt, nickel and manganese are completely precipitated at and over p_H 2.85, 3.24, 3.00 and 2.90 respectively and they may be estimated gravimetrically in presence of mineral acids and acetic acid, ammonia and caustic alkali. Below the respective p_H mentioned above, they are incompletely precipitated due to solubility and their point of incipient precipitation from hot solution, being at about the p_H 2.08, 2.14, 2.15 and 1.75 respectively. The highly crystalline salts after precipitation and washing may be dried at 110°-115° and weighed as the hydrated salts; zinc as $Zn(C_{14}H_8NO_2)_2 \cdot H_2O$; cobalt as $Co(C_{14}H_8NO_2)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and both nickel and manganese as $M(C_{14}H_8NO_2)_2 \cdot 2.5 H_2O$ (where $M=Ni$ or Mn). The cobalt salt may also be dried at 150°-155° when due to loss of water, it may be weighed as the anhydrous salt.

EXPERIMENTAL

In addition to the reagents mentioned previously (*loc. cit.*), sodium hydroxide of different normalities and sodium acetate were used here. They were of reagent quality. Here also an 1% solution of sodium benzoquinaldinate (1 g. of the benzoquinaldinic acid of m.p. 187° per 100 c.c. of the solution) was used.

Standard solutions.—Kahlbaum's pro-analysis granulated zinc was dissolved in concentrated nitric acid (pro-analysis) and made up to the desired volume. The zinc content per c.c. of the solution was determined by estimating zinc as sulphate by drying at a temperature between 450° and 740° (cf. Duval and Clerq, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1951, 5, 282) and as pyrophosphate.

Cobalt nitrate solution was prepared by dissolving cobalt nitrate (Merck & Co., Reagent) in a known volume of water. Cobalt in the solution was estimated electrolytically and also as sulphate by drying at 600° - 812° (cf. Duval and Duval, *ibid.*, 1951, 5, 84).

Schering-Kahlbaum's 'cobalt free' nickel sulphate was dissolved in a definite volume of water. Nickel in the solution was determined by dimethylglyoxime and by electro-deposition.

Manganese sulphate solution was obtained from manganese sulphate (E. Merck, pro-analysi) and standardised as sulphate by drying at a temperature between 200° and 940° (Duval and Dupuis, *ibid.*, 1949, 3, 589).

Preparation and Composition of the Zinc, Cobalt, Nickel and Manganese Salts of 5:6-Benzoquinaldinic Acid.—The salts were prepared in the same way as described for copper and cadmium salts in previous communications (*loc. cit.*) and dried at 110° - 115° . The dried salts were decomposed in the same way as was done in the case of cadmium (*loc. cit.*) and excepting nickel, other metals were estimated as the anhydrous sulphate. The nickel salt could not be estimated as the anhydrous sulphate as it decomposed to a basic salt (cf. Duval and Duval, *ibid.*, 1951, 5, 71) and hence estimated as the dimethylglyoximate. Results of analysis of the compounds are shown below.

Metal found.	Calc. from.	Metal calc.
Zn, 12.41, 12.45	ZnR*.H ₂ O	12.40%
Co, 10.92, 10.96	CoR. 2H ₂ O	10.94
Ni, 10.69, 10.72	NiR. 2.5H ₂ O	10.72
Mn, 10.08, 10.12	MnR. 2.5H ₂ O	10.10

* [R = (C₁₄H₈NO₂)₂]

The zinc salt is white; cobalt, cream-coloured; nickel, greenish and manganese, yellow. All of them are soluble in excess of dilute acids and in cyanide. The zinc salt is soluble also in excess of ammonia and alkali. Cobalt, nickel and manganese salts, on the other hand, are insoluble in ammonia. In moderately strong caustic soda solution both the nickel and manganese salts are decomposed to their hydroxides, but the cobalt salt dissolves on heating and reappears on cooling. Like the copper and cadmium salts, they are all insoluble in organic solvents such as ethyl alcohol, amyl alcohol, ether, benzene, carbon disulphide and carbon tetrachloride.

Precipitation limits for Zinc, Cobalt, Nickel and Manganese.—The precipitation limits were found in the same way as in the case of copper and cadmium (*loc. cit.*). Precipitates were obtained even at a dilution of 1 part in 50, 0.5, 0.5 and 100 million parts respectively.

Effect of Temperature on the Salts.—The procedure was the same as given in earlier papers (*loc. cit.*). The zinc salt with 1 H₂O was stable up to 140° and then lost water till at about 186° it became anhydrous and in which state it was stable up to 260° (Clement Duval of Sorbonne, Paris, private communication). The salts of nickel and manganese, like zinc, were stable with 2.5 H₂O up to 140° . At 180° the nickel salt lost 7.23% of water and the manganese salt about 6.60%. The cobalt salt, on the other hand, lost water completely at 150° though up to 130° it was stable with 2 moles of water.

Like the salts of copper and cadmium (*loc. cit.*), the cobalt salt dried at 110°-115° and at 150°-155° was analysed as the anhydrous sulphate in the same way as described above. [Found: Co (dried at 110°-115°), 10.90, 10.94; Co (dried at 150°-155°), 11.74, 11.69; loss of water, 6.64, 6.71. Calc. for Co (C₁₄H₈NO₂)₂: Co, 11.72; loss of 2H₂O, 6.68 per cent].

The results in Table I show that cobalt could be estimated according to the method given below either by drying at 110°-115° (to dihydrate) or at 150°-155° (to anhydrous salt).

TABLE I

No.	Cobalt taken.	Reagent soln.	p _n .	Dried at 110°-115°.		Dried at 150°-155°.	
				Co salt.	Co found.	Co salt.	Co found.
1	9.12 mg.	8.0 c.c.	3.93	83.4 mg.	9.12 mg.	77.8 mg.	9.12 mg.
2	9.12	8.0	5.52	83.4	9.12	78.0	9.14
3	9.12	8.0	8.95	83.2	9.10	77.7	9.11

Estimation of Zinc, Cobalt, Nickel and Manganese

The solution containing the metal ion was neutralised with dilute ammonia, using Wesselow's indicator, acidified with 1 c.c. of sulphuric acid (N/10) and diluted to about 200 c.c. It was then heated to boiling, precipitated with the reagent, digested, filtered etc. according to the method described in previous communications (*loc. cit.*) under copper and cadmium. Table II gives the data for zinc; Table III, for cobalt; Table IV, for nickel and Table V, for manganese.

TABLE II

Drying temp. = 110°-115°. Factor = 0.1240.

No.	Zn taken.	Reagent soln.	p _n .	Zn salt.	Zn found.	Error.
1	6.27 mg.	5.0 c.c.	3.67	50.6 mg.	6.27 mg.	Nil
2	10.04	8.0	3.66	87.9	10.03	-0.01 mg.
3	18.83	15.0	3.88	151.5	18.79	-0.04
4	25.10	20.0	3.70	202.4	25.10	Nil
5	37.65	30.2	3.75	304.0	37.70	+0.05

TABLE III

Drying temp. = 150°-155°. Factor = 0.1172.

No.	Co taken.	Reagent soln.	p _n .	Co salt.	Co found.	Error.
1	5.39 mg.	5.0 c.c.	3.72	46.0 mg.	5.39 mg.	Nil
2	9.70	9.0	3.70	8.8	9.70	Nil
3	21.56	19.8	3.70	183.6	21.53	-0.04 mg.
4	32.34	29.5	3.73	276.0	32.35	+0.01
5	43.12	39.0	3.76	368.6	43.19	+0.07

TABLE IV

Drying temp. = 110° - 115°. Factor = 0.1072.

No.	Ni taken.	Reagent soln	p_H	Ni salt.	Ni found.	Error.
1	4.24 mg.	3.8 c. c.	3.70	39.5 mg	4.23 mg	-0.01 mg.
2	10.61	9.5	3.72	99.0	10.61	Nil
3	15.02	14.4	3.68	148.7	15.94	+0.02
4	21.22	19.0	3.72	197.8	21.20	-0.02
5	31.83	28.8	3.78	297.1	31.85	+0.02

TABLE V

Drying temp. = 110° - 115°. Factor = 0.1010.

No.	Mn taken	Reagent soln.	p_H	Mn salt.	Mn found.	Error.
1	4.96 mg.	4.5 c. c.	3.70	49.2 mg.	4.97 mg.	+0.01 mg.
2	9.93	9.0	3.68	98.3	9.93	Nil
3	18.62	16.8	3.75	184.6	18.64	+0.02
4	24.82	22.5	3.70	246.0	24.85	+0.03
5	31.00	27.9	3.76	308.0	31.10	+0.10

TABLE VI

Drying temperature = 110° - 115°.

No.	Zn taken.	Acetic acid (1:1).	N/10- H ₂ SO ₄ .	Sodium acetate.	Reagent soln.	p_H .	Zn salt.	Zn found.	Error.
1	10.02 mg.	2 c. c.	—	—	8.0 c. c.	3.45	80.8 mg.	10.02 mg.	Nil
2	"	3	—	—	"	3.20	80.8	10.02	Nil
3	"	5	—	—	"	2.85	80.4	9.97	-0.05 mg.
4	"	6	—	—	"	2.72	79.4	9.85	-0.17
5	"	7	—	—	"	2.57	77.0	9.55	-0.47
6	8.02	2	—	4 g.	6.5	4.95	64.6	8.01	-0.01
7	"	4	—	4	"	4.32	64.6	8.01	-0.01
8	"	Just acidic	—	4	"	6.70	64.7	8.02	Nil
9	10.02	—	2 c. c.	—	8.0	3.35	80.7	10.01	-0.01
10	"	—	4	—	"	2.95	80.8	10.02	Nil
11	"	—	5	—	"	2.75	79.8	9.90	-0.12
12	"	—	6	—	"	2.60	79.2	9.82	-0.20
13	8.02	—	Just acidic	4	6.5	6.72	64.6	8.01	-0.01
*14	"	—	—	—	"	7.85	64.5	8.00	-0.02
*15	10.19	—	—	—	8.2	9.38	82.0	10.17	-0.02
†16	10.04	—	—	—	8.0	8.30	81.1	10.07	+0.03
†17	10.04	—	—	—	"	9.15	80.8	10.02	-0.02
†18	10.19	—	—	—	8.2	9.56	82.1	10.18	-0.01

From the table it follows that zinc can be estimated from and above p_H 2.85. Determined up to p_H 9.56.

Study of p_H ranges.—The method followed was the same as given above and the acidity was adjusted after neutralisation by acetic acid or sulphuric acid to obtain different p_H ranges. For higher p_H regions, *i. e.*, over about p_H 7, either the solution containing any one of the elements was treated with 2 g. of ammonium chloride and

rendered alkaline with dilute ammonia (2*N*) or caustic soda (*N*/₁₀) and then diluted and heated to boiling before the addition of the reagent, or to the solution was added the required quantity of the reagent first and then before dilution and boiling was rendered alkaline with dilute ammonia or caustic soda. The filtrate in each case was used for the measurement of p_H by Beckman p_H meter. The results for zinc, cobalt, nickel and manganese are given in Tables VI, VII, VIII and IX respectively.

TABLE VII

Drying temperature = 150°-155°.

No.	Co taken.	Acetic acid (1:1).	<i>N</i> / ₁₀ -H ₂ SO ₄ .	Sodium acetate.	Reagent soln.	p_H .	Co salt.	Co found.	Error.
1	9.12 mg.	1 c. c.	—	—	8.2 c. c.	3.74	77.9 mg.	9.13 mg.	+0.01 mg.
2	"	2	—	—	"	3.50	77.8	9.12	Nil
3	"	3	—	—	"	3.24	77.5	9.08	-0.04
4	"	4	—	—	"	3.10	76.6	8.98	-0.14
5	"	5	—	—	"	2.88	74.6	8.74	-0.38
6	"	2	—	4 c. c.	"	5.02	78.0	9.14	+0.02
7	"	Just acidic	—	4	"	6.68	77.6	9.10	-0.02
8	"	—	1 c. c.	—	"	3.68	77.8	9.12	Nil
9	"	—	2	—	"	3.40	77.8	9.12	Nil
10	"	—	3	—	"	3.30	77.6	9.10	-0.02
11	"	—	4	—	"	2.94	77.0	9.02	-0.10
12	"	—	Just acidic	2	"	6.41	77.6	9.10	-0.02
13	"	—	Do	4	"	6.70	77.9	9.13	+0.01
*14	"	—	—	—	"	9.20	77.8	9.12	Nil
*15	"	—	—	—	"	9.75	77.8	9.12	Nil
†16	8.62	—	—	—	7.3	8.12	73.6	8.63	+0.01
†17	"	—	—	—	"	9.55	73.7	8.64	+0.02
†18	10.23	—	—	—	8.2	9.82	87.3	10.23	Nil

From the table it is found that cobalt can be accurately estimated from p_H 3.24 to higher p_H ranges. Determined up to 9.82.

TABLE VIII

Drying temperature = 110°-115°.

No.	Ni taken.	Acetic acid.	<i>N</i> / ₁₀ -H ₂ SO ₄ .	Sodium acetate.	Reagent soln.	p_H .	Ni salt.	Ni found.	Error.
1	10.61 mg.	1 c. c.	—	—	9.5 c. c.	3.74	99.2 mg.	10.63 mg.	+0.02 mg.
2	"	2	—	—	"	3.54	99.0	10.61	Nil
3	"	3	—	—	"	3.30	99.0	10.61	Nil
4	"	4	—	—	"	3.15	98.6	10.57	-0.04
5	"	5	—	—	"	2.92	97.8	10.48	-0.13
6	"	6	—	—	"	2.70	96.3	10.32	-0.29
7	"	2	—	4 g.	"	5.05	99.1	10.62	+0.01
8	"	Just acidic	—	4	"	6.72	99.0	10.61	Nil
9	8.49	—	1 c. c.	—	7.70	3.72	79.3	8.50	+0.01
10	"	—	2	—	"	3.45	79.4	8.51	+0.02
11	"	—	3	—	"	3.25	79.2	8.49	Nil
12	"	—	4	—	"	3.00	78.8	8.45	-0.04
13	"	—	5	—	"	2.80	78.0	8.36	-0.13
14	"	—	Just acidic	2	"	6.45	79.1	8.48	-0.01
15	"	—	"	4	"	6.72	79.2	8.49	Nil
*16	"	—	—	—	"	8.30	79.0	8.47	-0.02
†17	"	—	—	—	"	10.30	79.1	8.48	-0.01
†18	"	—	—	—	"	10.50	79.4	8.51	+0.02
†19	"	—	—	—	"	11.00	79.2	8.49	Nil
*20	12.11	—	—	—	10.9	9.70	113.2	12.13	+0.02

From these results it follows that nickel can be accurately estimated from a p_H 3.0 to higher p_H ranges. Determined up to 11.0.

TABLE IX

Drying temperature = 110°-115°.

No.	Mn taken.	Acetic acid (1:1).	N/10. H ₂ SO ₄ .	Sodium acetate.	Reagent soln.	p _H .	Mn salt.	Mn found.	Error.
1	8.69 mg.	1 c.c.	—	—	7.90 c.c.	3.72	86.0 mg.	8.69 mg.	Nil
2	"	3	—	—	"	3.32	86.0	8.69	Nil
3	"	4	—	—	"	3.14	86.1	8.70	+0.01
4	"	5	—	—	"	2.90	85.6	8.65	-0.04
5	"	7	—	—	"	2.50	81.0	8.18	-0.51
6	"	Just acidic	—	4 g.	"	5.10	85.8	8.67	-0.02
7	"	"	—	4	"	6.58	86.1	8.70	+0.01
8	"	—	1 c.c.	—	"	3.68	86.0	8.69	Nil
9	"	—	2	—	"	3.48	85.9	8.68	-0.01
10	"	—	3	—	"	3.26	86.2	8.71	+0.02
11	"	—	4	—	"	2.98	85.8	8.66	-0.03
12	"	—	5	—	"	2.78	85.2	8.61	-0.08
13	"	—	6	—	"	2.62	84.0	8.48	-0.21
14	"	—	Just acidic	2	"	6.40	86.0	8.69	Nil
15	"	—	"	4	"	6.74	86.0	8.69	Nil
*16	"	—	—	—	"	8.24	85.1	8.70	+0.01
†17	"	—	—	—	"	8.62	86.2	8.71	+0.02
†18	"	—	—	—	"	8.70	86.0	8.69	Nil
*19	9.84	—	—	—	8.8	8.45	97.6	9.85	+0.01
†20	"	—	—	—	"	9.30	97.5	9.85	+0.01

It is evident from the table that manganese can be estimated from p_H 2.90 upwards. Determined up to 9.30.

In Tables VI to IX the marks (*) and (†) indicate that those experiments were done in ammoniacal and alkaline solutions respectively.

Incipient Precipitations for Zinc, Cobalt, Nickel and Manganese.—Working with hot solutions of gradually increasing p_H values, incipient precipitations were observed at well defined acidities with the different metal complexes—manganese, 1.75; zinc, 2.08; cobalt, 2.14; nickel, 2.15 (cf. Majumdar and De, *loc. cit.*).

Further work on the use of the reagent is in progress.

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